

Correction

Correction: Konidaris et al. Dating of the Lower Pleistocene Vertebrate Site of Tsiotra Vryssi (Mygdonia Basin, Greece): Biochronology, Magnetostratigraphy, and Cosmogenic Radionuclides. *Quaternary* 2021, 4, 1

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Error in Table/Figure

The authors wish to make the following corrections to their paper [1]:

In the published manuscript, the study presents diverse geochronological and biochronological data providing age constraints on the site of Tsiotra Vryssi (Mygdonia basin, Greece). One of the methods presented is based on burial ages from cosmogenic radionuclides. Table 2 of this study reports cosmogenic simple burial ages of 1.88 ± 0.16 Myr, 2.10 ± 0.18 Myr, and 1.98 ± 0.18 Myr (for samples COSMO 1, 2, and 3, respectively). However, after publication of the manuscript, a small error was found in the calculation of these ages. In particular, it concerns a typo in the MatLab code resulting in a too-low value for the fast muonic ^{10}Be production rate, which affected the last column of Table 2 with the simple burial ages. After correcting this mistake, the ‘corrected’ simple burial ages in Table 2 (as well as in Figure 9) should be 1.54 ± 0.10 Myr, 1.75 ± 0.10 Myr, and 1.62 ± 0.10 Myr. These ages, as were the original published ages, are the minimum possible burial ages from this technique. Therefore, the deposit with normal polarity containing the cosmogenic samples is attributed to the Olduvai subchron (1.95–1.78 Myr). The age of the overlying layer showing a reverse polarity and containing the vertebrate fossils is therefore the same as was originally published (<1.78 Myr), and overall, an age between 1.78 and ~ 1.5 Myr is proposed for the Tsiotra Vryssi fauna. We emphasize that the corrected ages mentioned here do not change the interpretations of the Konidaris et al. 2021 study, and we present this Erratum so that future studies using these data have access to the corrected values.

The correct versions of Table 2 and Figure 9 are provided below:

Figure 9. Correlation with the geomagnetic polarity time scale (GPTS) [82], simple burial ages provided by cosmogenic radionuclides, and biochronological range of selected large mammals from Tsiotra Vryssi.

Table 2. Cosmogenic radionuclide information for samples from the stratigraphic layer Geo 2b of Tsiotra Vryssi.

Sample ID	Lab ID	Grain Size (µm)	Qtz Dissolved (g)	m(²⁷ Al) (ppm)	²⁶ Al/ ²⁷ Al	1σ Error (%)	²⁶ Al Conc. 10 ⁴ atoms/g(qtz)	m(⁹ Be) (mg)	¹⁰ Be/ ⁹ Be	1σ Error (%)	¹⁰ Be Conc. 10 ⁴ atoms/g(qtz)	²⁶ Al/ ¹⁰ Be	Simple Burial Age (Myr)
COSMO 1	GL11	250–500	46.76	121	1.39 × 10 ⁻¹³	4.46	37.07 ± 1.91	0.3397	2.16 × 10 ⁻¹³	3.60	10.51 ± 0.42	3.53 ± 0.23	1.54 ± 0.10
COSMO 2	GL7	250–500	76.52	81	1.80 × 10 ⁻¹³	5.23	32.48 ± 1.70	0.2868	4.10 × 10 ⁻¹³	3.34	10.23 ± 0.34	3.18 ± 0.20	1.75 ± 0.10
COSMO 3	GL8	250–500	55.97	65	2.20 × 10 ⁻¹³	5.44	31.88 ± 1.74	0.2874	2.76 × 10 ⁻¹³	3.51	9.40 ± 0.33	3.39 ± 0.22	1.62 ± 0.10

The authors apologize for any inconvenience caused and state that the scientific conclusions are unaffected. The original publication has also been updated.

Reference

1. Konidaris, G.E.; Kostopoulos, D.S.; Maron, M.; Schaller, M.; Ehlers, T.A.; Aidona, E.; Marini, M.; Tourloukis, V.; Muttoni, G.; Koufos, G.D.; et al. Dating of the Lower Pleistocene Vertebrate Site of Tsiotra Vryssi (Mygdonia Basin, Greece): Biochronology, Magnetostratigraphy, and Cosmogenic Radionuclides. *Quaternary* **2021**, *4*, 1. [CrossRef]